
Alkaloids: A Continuation of Search for Antimalarial Leads

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Abstract Recently, there has been a resurgence of interests in the isolation and antiplasmodial evaluation of alkaloids from different medicinal plant species. The common heterocyclic moieties associated with bioactivity have continued to appear in the structures of the isolated alkaloids. Interestingly, when these compounds were tested against various strains of *Plasmodium falciparum*, they proved to demonstrate potent antiplasmodial activities. Herein a number of some alkaloids reported between 2014-2017 have been reviewed in order to serve as an inspiration towards optimizing some leads that could offer new antimalarial drugs.

Keywords Medicinal plants, alkaloids, isolation, antimalarial activity

Introduction

Malaria continues to be a major public health problem globally as approximately 214 million cases occur annually and 3.2 billion people are at risk of infection. Notably, this epidemic is more rampant in 97 tropical and subtropical countries and territories. Of which sub-Saharan Africa carries a disproportionately high share of the global malaria burden [1]. Particularly Nigeria which suffers the world's greatest malaria burden, with approximately 51 million cases and 207,000 deaths reported annually while 97 % of the total population is at risk of infection[2].

Alkaloids constitute the most important class of natural products providing drugs since ancient times. Famously, quinine and its derivatives used for the malarial treatment have demonstrated the ability of alkaloids to be used for the cure of infectious diseases [3].

In this mini-review, an attempt has been made to discuss some structurally diverse alkaloids isolated and evaluated against Plasmodium parasites between the years 2014-2017. The compounds are grouped based on their structural similarities.

Securinega Alkaloids

The isolation and antiplasmodial activity of the securinega alkaloids, viz. (+) – allonorsecurinine, *ent*-norsecurinine, nirurine, bubbialine, and epibubbialine (Figure 1) from *Phyllanthus fraternus* had been reported by Komlaga *et al* [4]. The compounds were evaluated against chloroquine resistant (W2) and sensitive (3D7) strains of *Plasmodium falciparum*. It was found that norsecurinine-type alkaloids; (+) – allonorsecurinine and *ent*- norsecurinine showed the strongest activity (2.57 ± 0.53 and 1.14 ± 0.32 μM) respectively against W2 strain, while showing a very weak activity against the 3D7 strain. On the other hand, the neonorsecurinanes, nirurine and bubbialine exhibited highest activity (4.19 ± 1.13 and 6.24 ± 0.58 μM) against 3D7, but showed a weak activity against W2 strain. Interestingly, epibubbialine exhibited generally similar level of activity (27.23 ± 2.94 and 23.67 ± 1.80 μM) against the two strains.

This work reported the first isolation of alkaloids from *Phyllanthus fraternus*, even though analogues had been described in close species of the *Phyllanthus* genus. Similarly, (+)- allonorsecurinine was described as a natural product for the first time. Furthermore, this investigation supports the biogenetic hypothesis for securinega alkaloid where neonorsecurinane-type skeleton is thought to be the biogenetic precursor of norsecurinane-type skeleton [4].

Figure 1: Securinega alkaloids

Naphthylisoquinoline Alkaloids

Tshitenge *et al.*, had isolated naphthylisoquinoline-containing alkaloids (Figure 2) designated ealaspasamines (**A-C**) from *Ancistrocladus ealaensis* [5]. The compounds were screened against chloroquine sensitive (NF54) and chloroquine resistant (K1) strains of the malaria parasite, *Plasmodium falciparum*. IC₅₀ values of 418nM (NF54) and 452nM (K1) were obtained for ealaspasamine **A**, 210nM (NF54) and 138nM (K1) for ealaspasamine **B**, 34nM (NF54) and 6.3nM (K1) for ealaspasamine **C**. The results demonstrated that ealaspasamine **C** had the highest activity against the resistant K1 strain. Furthermore, its cytotoxicity was found to be relatively low (6.0μM) compared to (61μM) and (>12.73μM) for ealaspasamine **A** and ealaspasamine **B** respectively.

Figure 2: Naphthylisoquinoline alkaloids

Isoquinoline Alkaloids

The isoquinoline alkaloids, (+)-sebiferin, (-)-milonine, (-)-boldine, (-)-norboldine, (-)-reticuline, and (-)-*O-O*-dimethylgrisabine (Figure 3) had been isolated from the bark of *Dehaasia longipedicellata* by Zahari *et al* [6]. Evaluation of the antiplasmodial activity of those compounds revealed that they possessed potent to moderate activity against chloroquine-resistant strain of *Plasmodium falciparum* (K1) with IC_{50} values of 22.46 μ g/ml, 0.097 μ g/ml, 2.602 μ g/ml, 9.284 μ g/ml, <30.400 μ g/ml and 0.031 μ g/ml respectively. Evidently, of the six compounds evaluated, (-)-*O-O*-dimethylgrisabine showed the most potent *in vitro* antiplasmodial activity (IC_{50} = 0.031 μ M), which was slightly better than the positive control chloroquine (IC_{50} = 0.090 μ M). In addition, (-)-milonine also displayed a strong inhibition capacity with an IC_{50} value of 0.097 μ M followed by (-)-boldine (IC_{50} = 2.602 μ M), (-)-norboldine (IC_{50} = 9.284 μ M), (+)-sebiferin (IC_{50} = 22.460 μ M), and (-)-reticuline (IC_{50} = <30.400 μ M).

Figure 3: Isoquinoline alkaloids

Figure 4: Bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids

Bisbenzylisoquinoline Alkaloids

The antiplasmodial activity of six bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids, namely (-)-gyrolidine, (+)-*O*-methyllimacusine, (+)-2-norobaberine, (+)-norstephasubine, (+)-stephasubine, and (+)-laurotetanine (Figure 4) isolated from *Alseodaphne corneri* had been reported [7]. The results showed that among the compounds evaluated, (+)-norstephasubine showed the most potent activity against chloroquine resistant K1 strain with an IC_{50} value of $0.116\mu M$ which was slightly higher than the standard chloroquine ($IC_{50} = 0.090\mu M$). Thus (+)-norstephasubine may be good candidate for development of potential antimalarial drug.

Cyclopeptide Alkaloids

Tuenter *et al.*, had reported the isolation of nine cyclopeptide alkaloids from the roots of *Ziziphus oxyphylla* [8]. Of the compounds isolated, the antiplasmodial activity of five (Figure 5) had been investigated. And it was found that *O*-desmethylnummularine-R showed the most promising antiplasmodial activity with IC_{50} value of $3.2\mu M$ against *P. falciparum* K1. Interestingly also, the IC_{50} of $> 64.0\mu M$ was evident for its cytotoxicity.

Figure 5: Cyclopeptide alkaloids

In a related work, the isolation and antiplasmodial activity of four other cyclopeptide alkaloids (Figure 6) from *Hymenocardia acida* had been reported. All four compounds showed moderate IC_{50} values ranging from 12.2 to $27.9\mu M$, the most active being hymenocardine-N-oxide [9].

Figure 6: Cyclopeptide alkaloids

Aporphine Alkaloid

The antiplasmodial activity of a new aporphine alkaloid, 7-*epi*-duguetine (Figure 7) isolated from *Dasymaschalon acuminatum* had been determined *in vitro* against the chloroquine resistant K1 strain of *Plasmodium falciparum*. It was found that the compound exhibited a potent activity with IC₅₀ value of 0.385 μg/mL [10].

Figure 7. Aporphine alkaloids

INDOLE ALKALOIDS

The indole-based alkaloids, namely Aspidoscarpine, uleine, apparacine, and N-methyl-tetrahydrolivacine (Figure 8) had been isolated from *Aspidosperma olivaceum*, and tested against *P. falciparum* chloroquine-resistant blood parasites (W2 clone). All IC₅₀ values for the compounds had been found to be below 10 μg/mL. In particular, Aspidoscarpine was found to show less toxicity with the SI value of 56 [11].

Figure 8: Indole alkaloids

Bisindole Alkaloid

Tschinda *et al.*, had reinvestigated the roots of *Strychnos icaja* and succeeded in isolating a minor alkaloid, named strychnobaillonine (Figure 9). Antiplasmodial evaluation of this bisindole compound showed potent activity against chloroquine-sensitive 3D7 strain of *Plasmodium falciparum* with an IC_{50} value of 1.1 μ M equivalent to 0.7 μ g/mL [12]. The cytotoxicity activity on normal human fibroblasts was also carried out, and it was found that at a concentration of 10 μ g/mL, strychnobaillonine exhibited no cytotoxicity toward the fibroblast, thus showing a good selectivity ($SI > 14$).

Strychnobaillonine

Figure 9: Bisindole alkaloid

Conclusions

In this mini-review, the isolation of a number of diverse alkaloids as well as their antiplasmodial activities has been discussed. Structurally, the compounds fall under the category of various well-known heterocyclic moieties associated with biological activity. The strains of the *Plasmodium falciparum* investigated represent the commonly encountered malaria parasites in patients, and a reasonable number of those alkaloids showed significant activity against them. It is thus envisioned that the compounds could serve as important leads towards developing new antimalarial drugs.

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